

REPORT:

A1.2.1: Review of existing standardised methods for characterising pressure drop and flow resistance applicable to microfluidics devices

Work package 1

2025-11-28

<https://mfmet.eu>

This report was written as part of activity A1.2.1 from the EPM Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET II) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2025, please visit <https://mfmet.eu>

Activity number	Activity description	Participants (Lead in bold)
A1.2.1 M6	FOG with the support from INESC MN, METU, UofG, DTI, IPQ, RISE and INRIM will review existing standardised methods for characterising pressure drop and flow resistance applicable to microfluidics devices. The review will consider different liquids at different temperatures. The review will explore the possibility of expanding pressure drop and flow resistance methodology and procedures to particle-laden flows. A report will compile the review performed within the activity and be shared to end-users and stakeholders.	FOG , INESC MN, METU, UofG, DTI, IPQ, RISE, INRIM

This report was written by:

Florestan Ogheard	FOG	<i>florestan.ogheard@gmail.com</i>
Elsa Batista	IPQ	<i>ebatista@ipq.pt</i>
Oliver Bükér	RISE	<i>oliver.buker@ri.se</i>
Thomas Schrøder Daugbjerg	DTI	<i>tsda@dti.dk</i>
Kevin Romieu	CETIAT	<i>kevin.romieu@cetiat.fr</i>
Vania Silverio	INESC MN	<i>vsilverio@inesc-mn.pt</i>

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EURAMET. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**EUROPEAN
PARTNERSHIP**

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

Contents

1. Scope.....	4
2. Review of standardized methods	4
Differential pressure	4
Hydrodynamic resistance.....	5
Pressure drop.....	6
PIV/PTV methods for pressure drop and flow resistance characterization	7
2.1 Other documented methods	8
3. Specificities of different temperatures & liquids.....	9
3.1. Effect of liquid viscosity	9
3.1.1. Newtonian liquids.....	9
3.1.2. Non-Newtonian liquids.....	10
3.2. Effect of liquid density	10
3.3. Effect of surface tension and wettability.....	10
3.4. Effect of temperature	11
4. Specificities of particle-laden flows	11
5. Proposals for particle-laden flows	12
6. References	13

1. Scope

This document reviews existing standardised methods for characterising pressure drop and flow resistance applicable to microfluidics devices. The review considers different liquids at different temperatures. The review explores the possibility of expanding pressure drop and flow resistance methodology and procedures to particle-laden flows.

2. Review of standardized methods

Differential pressure

In the context of flow metering differential pressure Δp is i.e. defined in the standard: ISO 5167-1:2022 Measurement of fluid flow by means of pressure differential devices inserted in circular cross-section conduits running full (ISO, 2022). The definition in that standard is quoted loosely and reworded below (ISO, 2022):

Differential pressure is the difference in pressure between two points in a flow line, one upstream and one downstream. The flow can pass through a measurement device between the two points. For example, the upstream pressure tapping can be located in front of the measuring instrument, while the downstream pressure tapping can be located in the throat of a nozzle, such as a Venturi nozzle. In this case, the differential pressure can be measured using a differential pressure device and related to the flow rate.

Here tapings are holes in the wall of a pipe, aligned with the inner surface, and to which a pressure sensor can be connected.

This definition of the differential pressure was also mentioned in a report of the project MFMET (20NRM02) (Akselli et al., 2022). (ISO, 2022) Here, Bernoulli's principle (Bernoulli's equation) provides the description for the relation between pressure and flow velocity (ISO, 2022; Kundu et al., 2016).

Related to this, the term pressure drop is defined in ISO 10991:2023 Microfluidics – Vocabulary, as the difference of pressure between two positions in the flow path, and that term is often used in microfluidics (ISO, 2023). Notice that pressure drop is a specific type of differential pressure. Pressure drop is always measured in the flow direction, whereas differential pressure is a measure of pressure difference between any two points, independent of the flow direction. In fact, differential pressure may be measured in systems with no flow.

The standard ISO 5167-1:2022 presents a detailed laboratory setup for differential pressure flow measurement (ISO, 2022). There the differential pressure is measured using a differential pressure transmitter connected to tapings at two positions on the pipe wall. Figure 1 shows a simplified conceptual drawing of measurement of pressure drop, which is a specific case of a differential pressure, measured along the flow.

Figure 1: A simplified conceptual drawing of a measurement of pressure drop, which is a specific case of differential pressure, measured between two tapings on a flow-carrying pipe. The instrument making the measurement is a differential pressure transmitter (DPT). Drawing inspired by the standard ISO5167-1:2022 (ISO, 2022).

Hydrodynamic resistance

Hydrodynamic resistance is defined in the standard: ISO 10991:2023 Microfluidics - Vocabulary (ISO, 2023). Hydrodynamic resistance, sometimes called hydraulic resistance, flow resistance or flow resistivity, see for example the term hydraulic resistance in the book by Bruus (Bruus, 2008). The definition in the ISO 10991:2023 standard is quoted loosely and reworded below:

Hydrodynamic resistance is the ratio of the pressure drop over a component to the flow rate through the component. The component may also be a system or subpart of a system.

The term hydrodynamic resistance is widely applicable in microfluidics. It is a useful quantity, because it gives knowledge of the relationship between flow rate and pressure in advance of any usage in the laboratory. Without it, the broad range of pressures and flow rates common in microfluidics makes it difficult to predict the flow behaviour of a component or system.

The hydrodynamic resistance R_{hyd} describes that a constant pressure drop Δp may drive a constant flow rate Q :

Equation 1

$$\Delta p = R_{hyd} Q$$

This description is related to a pressure-driven, steady-state flow of an incompressible Newtonian fluid in a confining channel (Bruus, 2008). If the flow is in the laminar regime, such cases are referred to as Poiseuille flow (Bruus, 2008). An analytical expression may be available for the hydrodynamic resistance, if the channel is straight, has a sufficiently simple geometry for the cross section, and the flow is in the laminar regime. For example, a rectangular channel with width w and height h , which is flat and wide ($h < w$), has the following expression (Bruus, 2008):

Equation 2

$$R_{hyd} = \frac{\Delta p}{Q} = \frac{12\eta L}{h^3 w} \frac{1}{1 - 0.630 \frac{h}{w}} \quad h < w$$

Here η is the dynamic viscosity, and L is the length of the straight channel. Other expressions for other geometries may be found in the literature (Bruus, 2008).

In 20NRM02 MFMET an extensive review of hydrodynamic resistance and experimental setups for determining hydrodynamic resistance was made. See for example Bker et al., Copeland et al., Ogheard et al. (Bker et al., 2023; Copeland et al., 2023; Ogheard, Daugbjerg, et al., 2024; Ogheard, Romieu, et al., 2024). Copeland et al. and Ogheard et al. describe setups for determining hydrodynamic resistance, and these are similar to the laboratory configurations for pressure drop presented in the below subsection on pressure drop (Copeland et al., 2023; Ogheard, Daugbjerg, et al., 2024).

Pressure drop

Pressure drop is defined in the standard: ISO 10991:2023 Microfluidics – Vocabulary (ISO, 2023). The definition in that standard is quoted loosely and reworded below:

Pressure drop is the difference between pressures at two positions in the microfluidic flow path.

Notice that the term pressure drop, which is commonly used in microfluidics, is related to the term differential pressure. Here it is repeated for convenience that pressure drop is a specific type of differential pressure. Pressure drop is always measured in the flow direction, whereas differential pressure is a measure of pressure difference between any two points, independent of the flow direction. In fact, differential pressure may be measured in systems with no flow.

Pressure drop was extensively covered in 20NRM02 MFMET, and several documents related to its measurement were produced. Examples include Copeland et al. and Ogheard et al. (Copeland et al., 2023; Ogheard, Daugbjerg, et al., 2024). The work by Copeland et al. presents three laboratory setups for measuring the pressure drop across a microfluidic device (Figure 2-4). In these configurations, a pressure controller generates the flow, which is monitored by a flow sensor (F). It should be noted that a flow sensor is not essential for the measuring the pressure drop. The three configurations are different in their use of a differential pressure sensor (P) or a pressure sensor (P), and the numbers of these sensors. (Ogheard, Daugbjerg, et al., 2024).

Figure 2: Pressure drop measurement with one flow sensor (F) and one pressure sensor (P) at the inlet of the microfluidic device, while the outlet is open to atmosphere. Figure reproduced from (Copeland et al., 2023).

Figure 3: Pressure drop measurement with one flow sensor (F) and a differential pressure sensor (P) in parallel with the microfluidic device. Figure reproduced from (Copeland et al., 2023).

Figure 4: Pressure drop measurement with one flow sensor (F) and two pressure sensors (P), one at the inlet and the other at the outlet of the microfluidic device. Figure reproduced from (Copeland et al., 2023).

The three configurations presented in Figure 2–4 are not exhaustive, and other configurations for measuring the pressure drop are also possible. Ogheard et al., for example, presented a configuration to measure both the pressure drop of the experimental setup both with and without the microfluidic device (Ogheard, Daugbjerg, et al., 2024). This enables the important subtraction of the contribution of the setup without the microfluidic device to the pressure drop, thereby determining only the pressure drop associated with the microfluidic device.

Note that the configurations in Figure 2–4 suggest simultaneous measurement of flow and pressure drop. Consequently, these configurations can also determine the hydrodynamic resistance of a microfluidic device using the formula, $R_{\text{hyd}} = \Delta p/Q$, as suggested in the subsection on hydrodynamic resistance above (Copeland et al., 2023; Ogheard, Daugbjerg, et al., 2024).

PIV/PTV methods for pressure drop and flow resistance characterization

In 20NRM02 MFMET A2.2.2 report, MFMET partners described the working principles and application of Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) and Particle Tracking Velocimetry (PTV) in microfluidics. To date, there are no normative standards for PIV or PTV methods or their application for characterising flow resistance or pressure drop in microfluidics. PTV and PIV enable indirect measurement of pressure drop by:

- Measurement of velocity profiles across channel cross-sections.
- Calculation of pressure gradients from velocity data using the Navier-Stokes equations simplified for laminar flow.
- Validation of experimental data against theoretical models such as the Hagen-Poiseuille's law for channels of circular or rectangular cross-sections.

In studies, PTV/PIV has been applied to straight channels, bifurcations and porous media to show how geometry and surface properties influence pressure drop. For example, PTV has resolved velocity gradients in channels with a height of only 50 μm , enabling precise estimation of pressure drop (Santiago et al., 1998).

PTV/PIV data allow the calculation of flow resistance (R_{hyd}) by:

- Simultaneous measurement of flow rate (Q) and pressure drop (ΔP).
- Applying the relationship $R_{\text{hyd}} = \Delta P/Q$ derived from the Hagen-Poiseuille equation.
- Evaluating the influence of channel shape, roughness, and fluid viscosity on resistance.

2.1 Other documented methods

In 20NRM02 MFMET A2.2.3 report, MFMET partners describe a flow resistance test setup in which a pressure controller, a flow meter, and the microfluidics chip are connected in series to evaluate the hydrodynamic resistance of one of the chip's channel. The report presents the test setup, the test procedure and experimental results obtained. In order to calculate the hydrodynamic resistance of the device under test itself, the authors describe how the hydrodynamic resistance determined for the control setup without the microfluidic chip is subtracted from the hydrodynamic resistance of the entire circuit with the microfluidic chip. In this documented example, an average experimental value of $5.63 \times 10^{12} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}/\text{m}^3$ is obtained for the device under test under all specified test conditions, with an associated expanded relative uncertainty of 42.8 % ($k=2$).

In 20NRM02 MFMET A2.4.3 report, MFMET partners evaluated the hydrodynamic resistance of the transfer standard chip using a flow controller, a pressure sensor and a flow meter in series, as illustrated in the figure 5.

Figure 5: setup for the measurement of hydrodynamic resistance. Figure reproduced from 20NRM02 MFMET A2.4.3 report.

The report describes the test protocol (§4.4.5), including guidelines for different channels' configurations, recommendations for measurement of inlet pressure, air purging and calculating the hydrodynamic resistance and the associated uncertainty.

MFMET partners applied the protocol presented in 20NRM02 MFMET A2.4.3 report and described in detail the results obtained by CETIAT, DTI, and the University of Glasgow for characterising hydrodynamic resistance (see §2.3.3). The most important results, findings and prospects for future work are presented in section 4.3 of 20NRM02 MFMET A2.4.4 report and a summarised below as essential information within the scope of this report:

For measurements of flow and hydrodynamic resistance, difficulties were found by all partners in driving and measuring flow through the leakage channels of the glass chips. This might be caused by the very small size of the leakage channels (150 μm x 2 μm) or partial to total blockage of the channels by small particles. Checking the chips with air at least confirmed the leakage channels were not totally blocked, and water was even observed flowing through for some chips (Figure 50). However, at least for the glass chip 1-1, the flow within the leakage channel was seen disturbed by small particles. This subject would deserve to be investigated in future works and protocols, and several partners already possess the tools to observe the behaviour of flows in such microchannels. The surface state inside the leakage channels might also play a more predominant role than inside the main channels. When characterizing hydrodynamic resistance of small channels that are associated with similarly high pressure and small volumetric flow, it may be very worth to consider a procedure like the one proposed by the University of Glasgow. Here the fluidic path upstream of the leakage channel was pressurised and then the pump was stopped, allowing a slowly decaying pressure and flow through the leakage channel. For very small channels, such a decay might reach conditions much closer to steady state laminar flow than a flow influenced by a pump. Such a protocol could also improve the efficiency of the plan of experiments, as it might allow for quicker measurements. It would however require an accurate description of the protocol and a test setup capable of recording the pressure and flow rate synchronously.

3. Specificities of different temperatures & liquids

3.1. Effect of liquid viscosity

3.1.1. Newtonian liquids

For Newtonian fluids, the relationship between pressure drop and viscosity is well described by the Hagen-Poiseuille equation, which states that pressure drop is directly proportional to fluid viscosity (μ) and channel length (L) and inversely proportional to the fourth power of the channel radius (r) in the case of cylindrical pipes:

$$\Delta P = \frac{8\mu L Q}{\pi r^4}$$

where Q is the volumetric flow rate.

As seen in section 2 Equation 2, dedicated formulas exist for microfluidic geometries and flow regimes where dynamic viscosity act as an input variable.

The viscosity of the fluid flowing through the microfluidic channel directly affects the pressure drop, with higher viscosities resulting in greater flow resistance and consequently higher pressure drops. In addition, different effects can be considered depending on the viscosity value:

- **High-Viscosity Fluids:** Pumping highly viscous fluids (e.g., 1×10^5 times more viscous than water) through typical microfluidic channels can require high pressures that often exceed the capacity of standard pump systems or the mechanical strength of device materials. Strategies to mitigate this include enlarging the channel cross-sectional area or reducing the channel length (Perry S.L. et al, 2010).
- **Low-Viscosity Fluids:** Selecting fluids with lower viscosity minimises pressure drop, and reduces the risk of device failure due to high pressure.

3.1.2. Non-Newtonian liquids

Non-Newtonian fluids such as blood, polymer solutions and suspensions exhibit complex rheological properties, including shear thinning, shear thickening and viscoelasticity. These properties significantly alter the pressure drop and flow resistance compared to Newtonian fluids:

- **Shear-Thinning Fluids:** The apparent viscosity decreases with increasing shear rate, resulting in a non-linear pressure drop behaviour. Experimental studies have shown that the pressure drop for shear-thinning fluids in microchannels can be predicted using modified models that consider the power law index and consistency coefficient of the fluid (Yang et al, 2019).
- **Viscoelastic Fluids:** The presence of viscoelasticity can lead to additional pressure losses due to normal stress differences and elastic effects, particularly in geometries with abrupt constrictions or expansions. For example, viscoelastic fluids in flow-focusing microfluidic devices exhibit different droplet formation regimes and pressure characteristics compared to Newtonian fluids (Chen et al, 2021).
- **Pressure Drop Models:** New correlations have been developed to estimate the frictional pressure drop gradient for non-Newtonian fluids, taking into account parameters such as the rheological properties of the fluid and the gas-liquid flow rate ratio (Kai et al, 2021).

3.2. Effect of liquid density

While the density (ρ) of the fluid has a minimal direct influence on pressure drop in laminar, incompressible flows (typical in microfluidics), it becomes relevant in scenarios involving inertial effects or multiphase flows:

- **Inertial Effects:** At higher flow rates or in channels with sudden expansions/constrictions, inertial forces (proportional to ρ) can contribute to pressure losses, although these effects are generally secondary to viscous forces in most microfluidic applications (Bruus et al, 2014).
- **Multiphase Flows:** In gas-liquid or liquid-liquid systems, density differences between phases influence flow patterns, droplet formation, and pressure drop. For instance, the Lockhart-Martinelli method, modified for non-Newtonian fluids, is used to predict two-phase pressure drops in microchannels (Kai et al, 2021).

3.3. Effect of surface tension and wettability

Surface tension (γ) and wettability (contact angle, θ) play a crucial role in capillary-driven flows, droplet formation and surface treatment, and influence pressure drop and flow resistance:

- **Capillary Pressure:** In channels with wettable surfaces ($\theta < 90^\circ$), negative capillary pressure draws the fluid into the channel, facilitating flow without external pumping. Conversely, hydrophobic surfaces ($\theta > 90^\circ$) resist fluid entry, increasing the required pressure to initiate flow (Khanjani et al, 2025)
- **Droplet Formation:** The capillary number ($Ca = \mu \cdot U / \gamma$, where U is the characteristic velocity) and viscosity ratio between the dispersed and continuous phases determine the droplet size and detachment. Higher surface tension or lower wettability can increase the pressure required for droplet breakup (Akepogu et al, 2023), (Stevens et al, 2023)

- **Surface treatment:** Surface treatments to reduce roughness or modify wettability can reduce frictional forces, thereby lowering pressure drop and flow resistance (Khanjani et al, 2025)

3.4. Effect of temperature

Temperature affects fluid properties such as viscosity, surface tension and density, thereby influencing pressure drop and flow resistance:

- **Viscosity:** Temperature changes can significantly alter fluid viscosity. For example, heating a fluid reduces its viscosity, which lowers the pressure drop and flow resistance. This principle is used utilised in thermally actuated microfluidic restrictors, where local heating adjusts the viscosity of the fluid in order to stabilise flow rates (Sodergren et al, 2021)
- **Surface Tension:** Temperature also affects surface tension, with higher temperatures generally reducing γ . This can impact capillary-driven flows and droplet formation, as shown by studies on temperature-actuated droplets in microfluidic channels (Khater et al, 2019), (Dos Reis Delgado et al, 2023)
- **Thermal Gradients:** Uneven heating can create thermal gradients that cause Marangoni flows or thermocapillary effects, further complicating the prediction of pressure drop and flow resistance (Dos Reis Delgado et al, 2023).

4. Specificities of particle-laden flows

When dealing with particle-laden flows, the following specificities can affect the measurement of pressure drop and flow resistance:

- **Clogging and Particle Aggregation:** Particles can aggregate or clog channels, leading to inaccurate pressure drop measurements and flow disruptions. Surface treatments and surfactants are used to mitigate these issues (Shen et al., 2020)
- **Wall Effects:** Surface roughness and particle-wall interactions affect pressure drop and flow resistance. The no-slip boundary condition and wall contact angles influence flow characteristics, especially with deformable particles like biological cells (Shen et al., 2020)

Moreover, for particle laden flows in the context of flow resistance, the fact that volumetric flow measurement is not well defined constitutes a challenge.

Assessment of particle-laden flows by computational tools faces also particular challenges:

- **Modelling Particle Interactions:** Accurate representation of particle-particle and particle-wall interactions is complex, especially for deformable particles like droplets and biological cells
- **Handling Deformable Particles:** Deformability introduces additional hydrodynamic forces and requires sophisticated models to capture shape changes and their impact on flow resistance
- **Computational Costs:** High particle concentrations and complex geometries increase computational demands, necessitating efficient numerical methods and mesh refinement strategies

The following table presents the key parameters influencing pressure drop and flow resistance:

Table 1: Key Parameters Influencing Pressure Drop and Flow Resistance

Parameter	Typical Range	Effect on Pressure Drop and Flow Resistance
Particle Volume Fraction	0.1% to 20%	Higher concentrations increase pressure drop due to particle interactions
Reynolds Number (Re)	< 1 to 100	Higher Re indicates inertial effects, influencing particle migration and pressure drop
Channel Geometry	10 μm to 500 μm width	Narrower channels increase resistance; aspect ratio affects particle focusing
Surface Roughness	0.1 μm to 1 μm	Increases wall friction, raises pressure drop
Particle Size	1 μm to 50 μm	Larger particles increase blockage and lift forces, affecting pressure drop
Fluid Viscosity	0.7 mPa·s (water) to 100 mPa·s (blood)	Higher viscosity increases resistance and pressure drop

5. Proposals for particle-laden flows

Considering the challenges and specificities of particle-laden and to cope with liquids properties & temperature effects on pressure drops and flow resistance, the following recommendations can be drawn:

- **Channel Surface Treatments:** Use of surfactants and surface coatings modifies channel surface chemistry, reducing particle aggregation and improving droplet formation and flow stability (Shen et al., 2020)
- **Particle Dispersion Techniques:** Optimizing particle dispersion through chemical or physical methods minimizes clogging and ensures uniform flow conditions (Shen et al., 2020)
- **Critical Parameters:** Particle volume fraction, Reynolds number, channel geometry, and surface roughness must be carefully controlled and characterized as they significantly influence pressure drop and flow resistance (Shen et al., 2020)
- **Material Selection:** Choosing materials with appropriate thermal and surface properties can help manage pressure drop and flow resistance. For example, PDMS is widely used due to its thermal stability and ease of surface modification (Estarki et al, 2023)
- **Flow Control Systems:** Active flow control, such as thermally actuated restrictors or feedback-controlled pumps, can compensate for variations in fluid properties and temperature, ensuring stable operation (Södergren et al, 2021)
- **Computational Modelling:** Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations are invaluable for predicting pressure drop and flow resistance, allowing researchers to optimize channel designs and operational parameters before fabrication (Somasekhara et al, 2017), and several recommendations can be drawn in order to improve the simulations accuracy:
 - **Discrete Phase Models:** Treat particles as discrete entities interacting with the fluid and channel walls, useful for rigid spheres and deformable droplets
 - **Particle-Resolved Simulations:** Resolve fluid flow around individual particles, capturing detailed particle-particle and particle-wall interactions but at higher computational cost
 - **Mesh Refinement:** Refining the mesh near particles and channel walls captures local flow disturbances and improves simulation accuracy (Bravan et al, 2022)

- **Rigid vs. Deformable Particles:** Treating particles as rigid simplifies simulations but may not capture the behaviour of biological cells or droplets accurately
- **Neglecting Brownian Motion:** Brownian motion is often neglected in macroscale simulations but may be significant for particles below 1 μm
- **Hybrid Eulerian-Lagrangian Models:** Combine the strengths of Eulerian fluid flow models with Lagrangian particle tracking for improved accuracy

6. References

Akselli, B., Ogheard, F., & Batista, E. (2022). MFMET A2.2.1 - Literature review of existing metrology and normative standards related to the flow properties and microfluidic devices. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6576473>

Batista, E., Bker, O., Romieu, K., Akselli, B., Akatay, A. A., Geršl, J., Kartmann, S., Moura, S., & Pellegrino, O. (2024). MFMET Deliverable 4 - Report on test protocols for liquid properties in microfluidic devices for use in pharmaceuticals, biomedical and mechanobiology applications. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11164544>

Batista, E., Furtado, A., Moura, S., Pellegrino, O., Akselli, B., & Ogheard, F. (2023). MFMET A2.3.2: Test protocols for liquid properties related to microfluidic devices. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7845225>

Bruus, H. (2008). Theoretical Microfluidics. Publisher: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780199235087.001.0001>

Bruus, H. (2014) Microscale Acoustofluidics, ed. T. Laurell and A. Lenshof, The Royal Society of Chemistry, ch. 1, pp. 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1039/9781849737067>

Bker, O., Copeland, M., Daugbjerg, T. S., Ogheard, F., Romieu, K., Batista, E., Silverio, V., Akselli, B., Geršl, J., Kartmann, S., & Lotters, J. (2024). MFMET Deliverable 3 - Calibration guide for the evaluation of flow-related quantities in microfluidic devices. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11164417>

Bker, O., Copeland, M., Daugbjerg, T. S., Ogheard, F., Romieu, K., Batista, E., Silverio, V., Akselli, B., Geršl, J., Kartmann, S., & Lotters, J. (2024). MFMET Deliverable 3 - Calibration guide for the evaluation of flow-related quantities in microfluidic devices. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11164417>

Chen, Q., Li, J., Song, Y., Chen, B., Christopher, D.M., Li, X. (2021) Pressure-driven microfluidic droplet formation in Newtonian and shear-thinning fluids in glass flow-focusing microchannels, International Journal of Multiphase Flow, 140:103648 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmultiphaseflow.2021.103648>

Copeland, M., Ogheard, F., Batista, E., & Heeren, H. van. (2023). Whitepaper flow resistivity testing. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7919134>

Copeland, M., Ogheard, F., Batista, E., & Silverio, V. (2023). MFMET A2.2.2: Development of test protocols for microfluidic devices. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7845431>

Dos-Reis-Delgado, A.A., Carmona-Dominguez, A., Sosa-Avalos, G., Jimenez-Saaib, I.H., Villegas-Cantu, K.E., Gallo-Villanueva, R.C., et al. (2023) Recent advances and challenges in temperature monitoring and control in microfluidic devices. Electrophoresis.; 44: 268–297. <https://doi.org/10.1002/elps.202200162>

- Estarki, H.E., Tareie, Z.S., Latifi, H. (2023) Pressure drop measurement in microfluidics channel by the Fabry-Perot diaphragm-based flow sensor, *Flow Measurement and Instrumentation*, 91:102355 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flowmeasinst.2023.102355>
- Feng, K., Zhang, H. (2021) Pressure drop and flow pattern of gas-non-Newtonian fluid two-phase flow in a square microchannel. *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, 173:158-169 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cherd.2021.07.010>
- García, B.F., Mousaviraad, M., Saraji, S. (2022) Verification and validation for microfluidic CFD simulations of Newtonian and non-Newtonian flows, *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, 107:557-573. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apm.2022.02.019>
- Geršl, J., Ogheard, F., Batista, E., & Silverio, V. (2022). MFMET A2.3.1 Literature review of existing metrology and normative standards related to the liquid properties and microfluidic devices. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8341288>
- ISO. (2022). ISO 5167-1:2022 Measurement of fluid flow by means of pressure differential devices inserted in circular cross-section conduits running full - Part 1: General principles and requirements. <https://www.iso.org/standard/79179.html>
- ISO. (2023). ISO 10991:2023 Microfluidics — Vocabulary. <https://www.iso.org/standard/82146.html>
- Khanjani, E., Fergola, A., López Martínez, J.A., Nazarnezhad, S., Casals Terre, J., Marasso, S.L., & Aghajanloo, B. (2025) Capillary microfluidics for diagnostic applications: fundamentals, mechanisms, and capillarics. *Front. Lab. Chip. Technol.* 4:1502127. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frlct.2025.1502127>
- Khater, A., Mohammadi, M., Mohamad, A., et al. (2019) Dynamics of temperature-actuated droplets within microfluidics. *Sci Rep* 9, 3832 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-40069-9>
- Kundu, P. K. ., Cohen, I. M., Dowling, D. R., & Tryggvason, G. (2016). *Fluid mechanics*. 6th ed. Academic Press : Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2012-0-00611-4>
- Ogheard, F. (2024). MFMET A3.2.5. Documented example of wettability test protocol. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11164616>
- Ogheard, F., Daugbjerg, T. S., Sluše, J., Geršl, J., Wippold, J. A., & Silverio, V. (2024). Assessing Hydrodynamic Resistance in Microfluidics: A Case Study. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202406.0049.v1>
- Ogheard, F., Romieu, K., Daugbjerg, T. S., Batista, E., & Silverio, V. (2024). MFMET A2.2.3 Documented example of the test protocol for hydrodynamic resistance, flow rate and volume. <https://zenodo.org/records/11239422>
- Pecnik, C., Romieu, K., Batista, E., Daugbjerg, T. S., Feltin, N., Yin, H., Kaal, J., Gärtner, C., Guha, S., Buesink, W., & Silverio, V. (2024). MFMET A2.4.4 technical report describing the design, fabrication, and calibration process of the transfer standards. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11402853>
- Perry, S.L., Higdon, J.J., Kenis, P.J. (2010) Design rules for pumping and metering of highly viscous fluids in microfluidics. *Lab Chip*. 10(22):3112-24. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c0lc00035c>
- Romieu, K., Batista, E., & Daugbjerg, T. S. (2024). MFMET A2.4.3 Documented example of the leakage transfer standards test. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11403006>
- Santiago, J. G., Wereley, S. T., Meinhart, C. D., Beebe, D. J., & Adrian, R. J. (1998). A particle image velocimetry system for microfluidics. *Experiments in Fluids*, 25(4):316–319. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s003480050256>

Shen, F., Ai, M., Ma, J., Li, Z., Xue, S. (2020) An Easy Method for Pressure Measurement in Microchannels Using Trapped Air Compression in a One-End-Sealed Capillary. *Micromachines (Basel)* 11(10):914 <https://doi.org/10.3390/mi11100914>

Södergren, S., Svensson, K. & Hjort, K. (2021) Microfluidic active pressure and flow stabiliser. *Sci Rep* 11, 22504 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-01865-4>

Sontti, S.G., Atta, A. (2017) CFD analysis of microfluidic droplet formation in non-Newtonian liquid, *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 330:245-261 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2017.07.097>

Stevens, M., Balaur, E., & Abbey, B. (2023) Computational simulation of the effects of interfacial tension in microfluidic flow focusing droplet generators. *Front. Phys.* 11:1060780. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphy.2023.1060780>

Yang, X., Weldetsadik, N.T., Hayat, Z., et al. (2019) Pressure drop of single phase flow in microchannels and its application in characterizing the apparent rheological property of fluids. *Microfluid Nanofluid* 23:75. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10404-019-2241-y>